

Oxford Tropical Research Ethics Committee

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Dr Van Tan Le
Centre for Tropical Medicine
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764 Vo Van Kiet Street
Ward 1, District 5
Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam

4 March 2020

Dear Dr Le

Full Title of Study: Clinical features, epidemiology and causes of pediatric encephalitis in southern Vietnam

OxTREC Reference: 7-20

Thank you for your letter of 24 February 2020 in which you have responded to the Committee's request for further clarification.

I am pleased to confirm that approval has now been granted for this study. This is valid for the first five years and is subject to receiving the local ethical approval (if this approval has not yet been received).

The documents approved for this study are as follows:

Documents:	Version:	Date:
OxTREC application form		
Protocol	V2.0	20/02/20
PIS/ICF	V2.0	20/02/20
Assent Form	V2.0	20/02/20
Peer Review Form		
PI Signature Form		

Any subsequent changes to the application must be submitted to the Committee as an Amendment. This should include a letter to give the reasons for the proposed modifications and all revised documents with changes tracked.

Please ensure that you submit a completed Annual Report form on every anniversary of this approval and a final End of Study Report. The relevant forms can be found on the OxTREC website: <https://researchsupport.admin.ox.ac.uk/governance/ethics/apply/xtrec>.

Finally, please note the following **important information**:

Tel: +44 (0)1865 (2)82106
Email: xtrec@admin.ox.ac.uk
Web: <https://researchsupport.admin.ox.ac.uk/governance/ethics>

Data safety—all studies

It is the responsibility of the PI to ensure that all data collected during the course of the study is stored and transferred safely and securely. Further guidance and advice is available from the [Research Data Team](#).

Studies that will involve storing human tissue samples in Oxford

As you are planning to import the samples into England, you will need to make arrangements before the samples are transferred to store them under the governance of a Human Tissue Authority (HTA) licence. It is a legal requirement that any tissue or fluid made up of or containing human cells to be used for the purpose of research is stored on premises licensed by the HTA unless covered by an exemption. OxTREC approval is not a recognised exemption. Further information may be found on the University's human tissue governance web pages: <https://researchsupport.admin.ox.ac.uk/governance/human-tissue>.

Yours sincerely

A handwritten signature in cursive script that reads 'Rebecca Bryant'.

Dr Rebecca Bryant
Research Ethics Manager, OxTREC